

The Most Useful Activities According to the Lesson Outcomes

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Abstract:

Upcoming article is devoted to the most useful activities according to the lesson outcomes. It will help readers to choose what kinds of activities will fit their lesson the most.

Keywords: types of activities, criteria for choosing activities, relevance between aims of the lesson and types of methods.

Introduction. The crucial part of the lesson planning is choosing the ways of delivering the information to the supposed audience, as it decides whether learners grasp a piece of knowledge or not. Teacher has to possess skills of psychologist and pedagogist in a professional level to make it in a proper way. Some students learn a new language more quickly and easily than others. This simple fact is known by all who have themselves learned a second language or taught those who are using their second language in school. However, there are other crucial factors influencing success that are largely beyond the control of the learner. These factors can be broadly categorized as internal and external. It is their complex interplay that determines the speed and facility with which the new language is learned. There are some factors that influence on learners' ability as:

Age: this factor dictates learners interest and major kind of activeness in particular period of person's development. Motivated, older learners can be very successful too, but usually struggle to achieve native-speaker-equivalent pronunciation and intonation.

Personality: Introverted or anxious learners usually make slower progress, particularly in the development of oral skills. They are less likely to take advantage of opportunities to speak, or to seek out such opportunities. More outgoing students will not worry about the inevitability of making mistakes. They will take risks, and thus will give themselves much more practice.

Motivation: it is the most important thing which helps learner acquire new language. Without being motivated, students easily lose interest in the process of studying. No matter how strong teacher forces them, outcomes will be ineffective.

We should take under consideration another factors that are not related to the learners' facilities. Being more particular, it also depends on teachers' proficiency. According to some internet sources teachers should follow a number of key points and some of them are going to be discussed next:

Main points in choosing materials teaching English

1. Understanding Students Needs: it will help teachers to meet students' needs and easily achieve goals. Without understanding learners' backgrounds, interests, and learning styles it would be impossible. This enables them to tailor their teaching methods to meet various requirements of the students, effectively. It also serves as a basic plan of whole course.
2. Clear Learning Objectives: Clearly defined learning objectives provide direction and purpose for both teachers and students. Further more, it supplies perfect time management and the fastest way to gain aims.
3. Active Learning: Engaging students in active learning experiences promotes a deeper understanding of the topics. Activities such as group discussions, hands-on experiments, role-playing, and problem-solving tasks encourage students to actively participate in various learning activities. The reason for that can be the fact that while moving around, students' brains activate some parts which are responsible for memory.
4. Differentiated Instruction: Teachers has to possess a number of techniques of providing instructions, as students can get bored easily.
5. Use of Technology: Implementing technology into the lesson process helps to keep learners motivated .Educational apps, multimedia resources, interactive whiteboards, and online collaborative tools can supplement traditional teaching methods and a positive appeal to Digital Education Methodology.
6. Formative Assessment: Regular assessment of student progress through quizzes, assignments, and classroom discussions provides valuable feedback for both teachers and students. It can increase learners' awareness of their own steps
7. Creating a Positive Learning Environment: Creating a safe and supportive classroom environment is important for students to feel comfortable and express themselves.

Lower, we are going to observe some basic methods of teaching foreign language which can be helpful in preparing activities for learners:

1. Grammar Translation Method

The strategy of teaching English language orientation depends on interpretation. The technique is the conventional or 'old-style method of learning a language. The main thought behind this strategy is that the students become proficient in English Grammar rules to translate various sentences easily. From my point of view this method would be the best way of training ESP learners at the beginning of course. The reason for that can be the fact, that adult students are more likely to have difficulties with immediate communication in target language.

2. The Direct Method

The Audio method is also known as the direct method, which involves thinking and communicating in English. This communication between the teacher and the student is strictly in English, and the student is barred from using their native language. This way helps everyone to work on their speaking language and try to improve it step by step. This method can be more profitable for using

within intermediate level learners. Because they don't have troubles with communication in target language

3. The Audio-Lingual Method

The audio-lingual methods emphasis was not on the understanding of words, but rather on the acquisition of structures and patterns in common everyday dialogue. Personally, I use it for students with kinesthetic and authentic learning types

4. Suggestopedia

The method involves using the environment, music, decorative, etc., for adopting the language. It depends a lot on the atmosphere and the physical environmental factors of the class. When teachers are made to use the Suggestopedia method there's a great deal of craftsmanship and music included. It is mostly used at the beginning of course to improve motivation of learners

5. Total Physical Response

Total Physical Response, also called TPR, is a method that includes body movements and hand gestures. According to some researches, using gestures and bright facial expressions persuades audience easier than others who do not use them

6. Communicative Language Teaching

There are some learning and teaching techniques that can be used in Communicative Language Teaching class, for example, role play, information gap, language exchanges, simulation, discussion, games, pair work, and group work. All these techniques can engage the learners in the communication process. The Communicative Language Teaching approach focuses on giving students the skills to clearly and confidently communicate in real-world situations with native speakers of their target language. Given method is one of the most fruitful approaches. It is

7. Task-Based Learning

Task-based language teaching is also called task-based instruction. The motive of this way to deal with learning is task finishing. Typically, the teacher sets relevant and exciting tasks. Then, students are required to complete their tasks in English to finish the job with as few mistakes as expected. Such assignments can incorporate visiting a specialist, directing a meeting, or calling customer care for help. Task-based learning is a way of language learning where learners are given interactive tasks to complete. To do this, they need to communicate. Once the task is complete, then the teacher discusses the language used.

8. Lexical Approach

The Lexical approach depends on computer studies with the most customarily utilized words. This approach in teaching centers around vocabulary securing and teaching lexical lumps arranged by their recurrence and use. Lexical approach demands higher level students rather than previous approaches.

Concluding the information mentioned above, I can assert that being a teacher means keeping a perfect balance among method, technique and content of the lesson. Also teacher should take into consideration individual peculiarities of every student and class profile at the same time. Activities should be chosen according to learning styles. Auditory learners learn through listening. As such, attending lectures, tutorials, and group discussions are absolutely essential for these learners. It can also be really helpful to engage in group discussions about course concepts and topics-create a weekly study group to get together weekly just to talk about the things being discussed in lectures. Visual learners learn through seeing, so tools like diagrams, flowcharts, pictures and symbols can be key to understanding new concepts. Other tricks to try for visual learners include spatially

rearranging your page instead of writing across a page horizontally, write in a way that is more descriptive of the relationship being described. Kinesthetic Learners learn through doing. This is perhaps the most challenging learning style for university students, as there are not always many opportunities to engage in hands on learning in lectures.

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